

DAMAGE MECHANISMS AND STIFFNESS DEGRADATION
IN GRAPHITE/EPOXY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Damage mechanisms and stiffness reduction were studied in crossply graphite/epoxy laminates subjected to tensile cyclic loading. Damage consists of transverse matrix cracking, longitudinal matrix cracking, delaminations at the intersections of matrix cracks, and fiber fracture. The reduction in residual axial modulus, even in normalized form, is a function of the cyclic stress level. The characteristic features of the stiffness reduction curves are: (1) initial drop corresponding to transverse matrix cracking during the first loading cycle, (2) gradual reduction or plateau corresponding to crack multiplication, and (3) accelerated reduction corresponding to longitudinal matrix cracking, delaminations and fiber fractures.

INTRODUCTION

Damage in composite laminates consists of the development and accumulation of numerous defects. The basic failure mechanisms, i.e., intralaminar and interlaminar matrix failures, have been observed and identified [1-3]. They can be studied and characterized by means of a variety of non-destructive methods, such as X-radiography, ultrasonics, acoustic emission, and edge replication. Under fatigue conditions, damage in crossply laminates consists of transverse matrix cracking, longitudinal matrix cracking, delaminations at the intersections of matrix cracks, and fiber fractures [4].

The state of damage is intimately related to the three most important properties of the material, stiffness, strength and life. Of these three properties, stiffness is related to damage in a more deterministic way. Furthermore, stiffness can be measured frequently during damage development in a nondestructive manner. Thus, stiffness is an important measure of damage [5]. Some analytical procedures have been developed for relating stiffness reduction to damage state for some forms of damage, such as matrix cracking and delaminations [6-9]. Some of these theories require the determination of "material" or laminate parameters by means of some form of curve fitting of experimental data. Theories based on a more mechanistic point of view require extensive computer runs even for thin laminates. The dynamics of damage development or damage growth is not well understood. For this reason, to the authors' knowledge, there is no theory available de-

scribing a stiffness degradation law for a general laminate as a function of loading history. Such a law would be essential for the development of a cumulative damage model. The importance of residual stiffness is based on the assumption that it is sufficient to describe damage, although no direct relationship has been proven relating residual stiffness, residual strength and residual life.

This paper deals with a specific aspect of this problem. An investigation was conducted of damage mechanisms and associated stiffness reduction of crossply graphite/epoxy laminates.

DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT

Under monotonic tensile loading, the predominant form of damage in crossply laminates is transverse matrix cracking. Longitudinal matrix cracking and delaminations occur at or very near failure.

The stress-strain curve to failure of a typical crossply laminate consists of three characteristic regions (Fig. 1): (1) a linear elastic region without any discernible damage, (2) a region of decreasing stiffness corresponding to transverse matrix crack initiation and multiplication, and (3) a nearly linear region of stabilized stiffness corresponding to the limiting crack density or characteristic damage state (CDS).

Figure 1. Stress-strain and stress versus crack density curves for $[0/90_2]_S$ graphite/epoxy specimens under uniaxial tensile loading.

Damage under tensile cyclic loading consists of transverse matrix cracking, longitudinal matrix cracking, delaminations at the intersections of matrix cracks, and fiber fracture. Damage mechanisms and damage development depend on the cyclic stress level and thereby on the state of damage produced during the first loading cycle. Three characteristic ranges of cyclic stress level can be selected, corresponding to the three regions of the quasi-static stress-strain curve (Fig. 1).

For the $[0/90]_2$ graphite/epoxy laminate studied, the three characteristic ranges are as follows: (1) cyclic stress 0 to 0.35 times the static strength, corresponding to linear elastic response and no initial damage, (2) cyclic stress 0.35 to 0.66 times the static strength corresponding to the region of decreasing stiffness and transverse matrix cracking, and (3) cyclic stress more than 0.66 times the static strength corresponding to the quasi-linear region following the characteristic damage state of the transverse layer.

Damage development was studied for the $[0/90]_2$ laminate at six different cyclic stress levels, corresponding to various stages of deformation in a quasi-static tension test. Damage mechanisms were characterized by means of penetrant-enhanced X-radiography. Typical radiographs for two characteristic cyclic stress levels, 53% and 85% of the static strength, are shown in Fig. 2. In all cases the first stage of damage development consists of transverse matrix cracking which generally increases in density with number of cycles as shown in Fig. 3.

At the lowest cyclic stress level of 28% of the static strength, there is a small number of transverse cracks after the first cycle. Transverse cracking increases gradually with number of cycles, but at one million cycles the crack density is still much lower than that at the CDS level. At the intermediate cyclic stress level of 53%, there is appreciable transverse matrix cracking after the first cycle, which increases gradually with number of cycles. However, the crack density is still below the CDS level after one million cycles. At the highest stress level of 85% of the static strength, transverse matrix cracking approaches or reaches the CDS level during the first cycle. Thereafter, there is no increase or only a slight increase in crack density, which remains constant for a large portion of the lifetime of the specimen. At some point, longitudinal matrix cracking develops with areas of delamination at the intersections of transverse and longitudinal cracks, followed by fiber fractures. It has been observed that this last stage of damage development begins at approximately 80% of the logarithmic lifetime of the specimen ($\log n/\log N$) for all cyclic stress levels. This was true in the cases where the cyclic stress was high enough to produce failure within an observable number of cycles.

STIFFNESS DEGRADATION

The reduction in residual axial modulus follows closely the observed damage development. When the maximum applied cyclic stress is below but near the static level of crack initiation, the stress-strain curve is linear and does not change up to a certain number of cycles. Thereafter, there is a definite reduction in modulus associated with transverse matrix cracking (Fig. 4). When the maximum cyclic stress is above the static CDS level, there is a drastic change in the stress-strain curve between the first and second cycles; thereafter, the change is very gradual, as shown in Fig. 5 for the $[0/90]_{4S}$ laminate. The stress-strain curve beyond the second cycle displays the characteristics of the 0-deg laminate, i.e., upward concavity. As the number of cycles increases, the stress-strain curve straightens out

(a) Cyclic stress: 414 MPa (60 ksi)

(b) Cyclic stress: 662 MPa (96 ksi)

Figure 2. X-radiographs of [0/90]_s graphite/epoxy laminate subjected to fatigue loading for various numbers of cycles.

Figure 3. Crack density variation with number of cycles for three different cyclic stress levels.

Figure 4. Stress-strain curves for [0/90₄]_s graphite/epoxy specimen during the first and millionth fatigue cycles.

Figure 5. Stress-strain curves for $[0/90_4]_s$ graphite/epoxy specimen at various stages of fatigue life.

and the initial modulus decreases gradually.

Residual modulus degradation was studied for the $[0/90_2]_s$ laminate at six different cyclic stress levels, corresponding to various stages of deformation and damage development in a quasi-static tension test. The results are best described in the form of normalized residual modulus as a function of the normalized logarithmic fatigue life ($\log n/\log N$). This requires the measurement or estimation of the fatigue life, N , of the specimen. For fatigue tests with a stress amplitude below 66% of the static strength it is not practical to measure the fatigue life directly. It is therefore necessary to estimate it. This was done by estimating the number of cycles necessary to reach the characteristic damage state (CDS life) and the residual life after attainment of the CDS.

The CDS life was estimated in two different ways: (1) by extrapolation of the crack density curves of Fig. 3 to the crack density at the CDS level (18.1 cracks/cm) and (2) by measuring residual modulus and extrapolating the residual modulus versus life curve to the value of 89% of the initial modulus, which is known to correspond to the CDS level.

Subsequently, the residual life after the CDS was estimated using lamination theory to calculate the stress in the 0-deg plies after reaching the CDS level. This stress was substituted in the equation (second order fit) of the S-N curve for the unsupported 0-deg lamina to obtain the remaining life, n_{res} .

The entire fatigue life of a specimen was obtained as follows:

$$N = n_{CDS} + n_{res}$$

where

N = fatigue life

n_{CDS} , n_{res} = CDS life and residual life after CDS, respectively

Alternatively, assuming that the CDS level is reached when

$$\log (n_{\text{CDS}}) / \log N = 0.8$$

we obtain

$$N = (n_{\text{CDS}})^{1.25}$$

Results for three characteristic levels of cyclic stress are shown in Figs. 6, 7 and 8. These curves reflect some or all of the three stages of damage development. The characteristic features of the stiffness reduction curve are: (1) initial drop corresponding to transverse matrix cracking during the first loading cycle, (2) gradual reduction or plateau corresponding to crack multiplication up to the CDS level or to a CDS level reached after the first few cycles, and (3) accelerated reduction corresponding to longitudinal matrix cracking, delaminations and fiber fractures in the last 20% of the normalized logarithmic lifetime.

It is seen from the above that the normalized residual axial modulus is a function of the cyclic stress level and the corresponding stage of damage development. Thus, residual stiffness, even in normalized form, cannot be represented by a single curve but rather by a family of curves with the cyclic stress level as a parameter (Fig. 9). These curves share one common branch, the last portion associated with longitudinal matrix cracking and fiber fractures in the last 20% of the normalized logarithmic lifetime.

Figure 6. Normalized residual modulus as a function of life for cyclic stress level of 28% of static strength.

Figure 7. Normalized residual modulus as a function of life for cyclic stress level of 53% of static strength.

Figure 8. Normalized residual modulus as a function of life for cyclic stress level of 85% of static strength.

Figure 9. Normalized residual axial modulus curves for $[0/90_2]_s$ graphite/epoxy laminate.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

Damage mechanisms and associated stiffness reduction were studied in crossply graphite/epoxy laminates under cyclic tensile loading. Damage development depends on the applied cyclic stress level and consists of three stages: (1) damage occurring during the first fatigue cycle consisting of transverse matrix cracking, (2) damage developing during the first 80% of the logarithmic lifetime of the material and consisting of multiplication of transverse matrix cracks up to the CDS level, and (3) damage occurring in the last 20% of the logarithmic lifetime and consisting of longitudinal matrix cracking, local delaminations and fiber fractures.

The associated reduction in axial modulus was found to be closely related to the damage development. The curves for normalized residual axial modulus were found to depend on the cyclic stress level. Thus, the normalized residual modulus cannot be represented by a single curve but rather by a parametric family of curves with the cyclic stress level as a parameter. The latter is expressed as a percentage of the static tensile strength. The characteristic features of the typical residual modulus curve are:

(1) initial drop due to first cycle damage, (2) gradual reduction or plateau due to transverse crack multiplication or saturation, and (3) accelerated reduction corresponding to longitudinal matrix cracking, local delaminations and fiber fractures. There is evidence that the last branch is common to all residual modulus curves and covers the last 20% of the logarithmic lifetime of the material ($\log n/\log N$).

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